

Prevalence of Psychiatric and Mental Health Disorders among Population in Mosul City for the Period (2018-2022)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Most people on the planet suffer from mental and psychiatric illnesses. Finally, because of Iraq's lengthy history of terrorist attacks and conflicts that have severely impeded progress, little research has been done on the incidence of psychiatric and mental health diseases. The study's goals were to identify the top 6 instances for both genders and to paint a comprehensive picture of the psychiatric and mental health disorders cases that were recorded in Mosul city between 2018 and 2022.

Methods and Materials: The current retrospective investigation was conducted in Mosul City's teaching hospitals that house psychiatric units. The current study was carried out between March 1st, 2023 and May 31st, 2023. For the previous five years, from 2018 to 2022, the data was collected from official records of teaching hospitals with mental units located in Mosul City.

Results: A total of 2550 cases of all psychiatric and mental health disorders in Mosul city were recorded from 2018 to 2022. Of these, 65.3 % were females and 34.7 % were males. The mean of age for the study sample is 40.40 "(SD= ±5.60)". Results also showed that the maximum percentage of the sample (23.8 %) are in the age group of (27-34) years old, though the lowest percentage of the study sample (7.4%) are at the age group of (51-58) years old. For both genders, depression was the most common psychiatric disorder, it is accounted for (850) cases, followed by anxiety disorders.

Conclusion: Depression is on the top of six psychiatric and mental health disorders and is on the rising trend.

KEYWORDS: Prevalence, Psychiatric and Mental Health Disorders, Population.

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INTRODUCTION

Iraq is a Middle Eastern nation home of 41 million mostly Muslim citizens (1). The Iraqi nation has endured extremely trying times for many years, including bloodshed, repression, and protracted conflicts. These upsetting incidents have a significant negative impact on both physical and mental health (2). Iraq's psychiatric health services have traditionally been hospital-based and highly concentrated in metropolitan areas, with one psychiatrist per 300,000 people prior to 2003 dropping to one psychiatrist per million until recently (3). Internal displacement has been the main issue affecting the mental health of Iraqis recently, especially during the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS) assault (4). According to "The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)", by the conclusion Nowadays, psychiatric

disorder is seen as a medical problem with symptoms causing discontent with one's characteristics, abilities, and accomplishments; ineffective or unsatisfying interpersonal relationships; dissatisfaction with one's place in the world; ineffective coping with life events; and lack of personal growth (5,6). Psychiatric disorders are more common in women than in men. According to reports from the World Health Organization, depression will account for the largest portion of women's sickness burden by 2020. Psychological and mental disorders are linked to stress, wartime experiences, and maltreatment (7). Globally, 3.6% of people experience anxiety, and 4.4% of people suffer from depression (8). Women have a higher percentage of the population with anxiety and depression diagnoses (9). In the MENA region, sadness and PTSD are regarded as the most

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prevalent psychiatric diseases (10). The mental illness "depression" is consistently ranked in the top 25 primary reasons for disability adjusted life years (11). Due to political unrest, conflicts, and physical obstacles to health care resulting from poor transportation and distance, the people of this nation have endured years of difficult circumstances (12). Given the socioeconomic status-related parameters (13, 14), Given that psychiatric and mental illness are linked to stress, abuse history, and other factors (15,16), Iraqi women are probably more susceptible to psychiatric and mental illnesses. Additionally, it is extremely difficult to provide patients with the necessary services due to Iraq's inadequate mental health infrastructure. For instance, there are only four psychiatrists for every one million individuals. Doctors Without Borders conducted a research that revealed deficiencies in mental health care provided to communities and institutions (17). The present study aimed to identify the greatest number of cases of psychiatric and mental health illnesses that were

registered in Mosul city between 2018 and 2022, and to provide a comprehensive picture of those cases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The retrospective investigation was carried out at the Ibn-sena and Al Salam teaching hospitals in Mosul, which are known for having psychiatric departments. The current investigation ran from the start of March 2023 to the conclusion of May 2023. For the previous five years, from 2018 to 2022, all data was gathered from the official records of teaching hospitals with psychiatric units located in Mosul City. Over the course of five years, from 2018 to 2022, 2,550 people with psychiatric and mental health illnesses made up the study sample. The records contained information that could be accessed, such as the kind of mental illness, age, gender, and geographic location, which included the neighborhoods and areas on both sides of Mosul City.

RESULTS

Table 1: The Socio-demographical characteristics of the study sample. (N=2550)

	Groups	Total study Sample (N = 2550)	
		Frequency	Percentage
Age (Years)	(3 – 10)	153	6 %
	(11 – 18)	199	7.8 %
	(19 – 26)	316	12.4 %
	(27 – 34)	609	23.8 %
	(35-42)	566	22.3 %
	(43-50)	252	9.9 %
	(51-58)	189	7.4 %
	(59-66)	266	10.4 %
	Type	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	886	34.7%
	Female	1664	65.3 %
Residency	Classes	Frequency	Percentage
	Right side	2079	81.5 %
	Left side	471	18.5 %

Table 2: Total psychiatric and mental health disorders (N=2550) in Mosul city distributed by geographic area from 2018 to 2022.

Geographic area	Frequency	Percentage %
Almedan	425	17
Mosul Gdeda	372	14
Nablis	326	12
Kazrag	285	11
Zangely	222	8.7
Dchat Barga	207	8.1
Sabaawi	199	7
AlShafa	100	3.9
Alantessar	95	3.7
Alyarmuk	90	3.5

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Alqudis	89	3.4
Sumer	88	3.4
Wadi Hajar	52	2

Figure 1. Distribution of the study sample according to geographic areas of Mosul city throughout the past 5 years for the period from 2018 to 2022.

Table 3: Prevalence of top six psychiatric and mental health disorders in Mosul city according to years from 2018 to 2022.

Types of Disorders	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Total
Depression	109	122	187	200	232	850
Anxiety	198	103	185	89	91	666
Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)	299	106	52	51	13	521
Schizophrenia	52	40	102	107	54	355
Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD)	32	26	8	28	6	100
Autism	11	18	10	9	10	58

Figure 2: The six(6) most common psychiatric and mental health disorders among adult males and females in Mosul city through a 5-years for the period from 2018 to 2022.

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DISCUSSION

From 2018 to 2022, Mosul city registered 2550 cases of all psychiatric and mental health diseases. Of them, 34.7% were men and 65.3% were women. The participants' average age is 40.40 (SD = ±5.60). The results further demonstrated that the age group of (27–34) years old accounts for the largest percentage of the sample (23.8%), while the age group of (51–58) years old accounts for the lowest percentage of instances (7.4%). Anxiety disorders were the most common psychiatric disorder, accounting for 33.4% of the study sample with 850 cases, followed by depression. These outcomes align with the Healing Iraqis website (17). According to a study by Lafta and her colleagues, 45.5% of junior doctors in Iraq reported having depressed symptoms, and there was a strong correlation observed between reporting depressive symptoms and being exposed to violence at work (18). The study by Shukrya and her colleagues indicated that depression affects 70.5% of parents of children with cancer. It also found that moms experience depression at a higher rate than fathers (19). The majority of Iraqis experienced anxiety at various points in their lives. However, a prevalence percentage of (47.9%) (20) indicates that doctors and medical students have high anxiety levels. The majority of instances came from Mosul's right side; that is, 81.5% of the cases came from areas and quarters on the right side of the city, with the remaining 18.5% coming from areas and quarters on the left. As a result, from 2018 to 2022, this study documented the changing epidemiologic patterns for several psychiatric and mental health diseases in Mosul City. This variance is thought to be driven by a variety of factors, primarily security-related circumstances, such as after ISIS-held area has recovered, particularly after 2017.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There was difficulty in collecting data due to the bias of society, which is strict in revealing the secrets of mental illness. The current study recommend the ministry of health to plan for increasing the awareness of the population regarding psychiatric and mental health disorders for early visiting the psychiatrists and early treatment. The study also recommend the ministry of health to put a strategy of regular screening for psychiatric disorders by providing a specialized psychiatric centers inside Mosul city.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that the depression is on the top of six psychiatric and mental health disorders and is on the rising trend.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

None declared.

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